

STADIEM

STARTUP DRIVEN INNOVATION IN EUROPEAN MEDIA

D5.3 IMPACT METHODOLOGICAL FRAMEWORK

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Abstract	The deliverable gives an overview of the methodological framework of the impact assessment of the STADIEM project and lists the impact measuring verticals, data gathering points and methods, responsible consortium partners, and the impact implementation process.
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PU	Public, fully open, e.g. web	✓
CL	Classified, information as referred to in Commission Decision 2001/844/EC	
CO	Confidential to STADIEM project and Commission Services	

* R: Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports)

DEM: Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs

DEC: Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.

OTHER: Software, technical diagram, etc.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable gives an overview of the Impact Methodological framework for the European mediatech scaling and corporate piloting project STADIEM.

Firstly, it presents the Impact assessment methodology devised during the project's first year created by the impact lead Storytek and validated by the consortium. It then proceeds to explain the Minimum Viable Impact Assessment concept based on the *Build-Measure-Learn principle*, allowing the impact of the project to be mapped continuously in an experiment-driven fashion and delivering results to be implemented as lessons learned during the lifecycle of the project.

It also demonstrates the four verticals where STADIEM focuses its impact assessment: 1) ecosystem, 2) programme framework, 3) delivery, and 4) communication and dissemination.

The deliverable then presents an extensive overview of impact assessment points, the frequency of the assessment, output format, and the responsible consortium members.

The second part of the deliverable focuses on the suggested implementation of the impact assessment. It presents the critical deliverables across the project where impact results will be presented as well as the three-year implementation process for impact result analysis and publication, that will start to publish the impact results from year two onwards based on the findings from the first cohort of STADIEM supported start-ups and scale-ups.

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1 STADIEM IMPACT ASSESSMENT METHODOLOGY

1.1 ASSESSING STADIEM IMPACT. THE MVIA MODEL WITH CONTINUOUS LEARNING AND IMPLEMENTATION

STADIEM is a one-of-a-kind pioneering media innovation ecosystem development programme, a virtual acceleration and co creation platform, between European mediatech scale-ups and corporates, bringing together several disciplines from start-up founder support, business development & upskilling, technical capacity building, service piloting, and corporate stakeholder management. The programme is created and managed by the STADIEM consortium consisting of key players in the European mediatech ecosystem including VRT, Media City Bergen, The Next Media Accelerator and Storytek, with partners Exit Academy, Martel Innovate, EBU and F6s. Thus, the critical outcomes of the project are not only confined to the success metrics of participating beneficiaries, i.e. selected start-ups and scale-ups, and their pilots with European corporates, but more broadly also the data about systemic blockers and opportunities for scaling, start-up and founder growth, corporate needs, opportunities and blockers, and largely lessons learned from diverse areas of the project.

Therefore, assessing impact and continuously collecting feedback from the project's data points and KPIs described below, implementing the results from KPI assessment and mitigation and lessons learned from the deployment of the project are a critical capacity in managing the STADIEM project and its programme deployment.

To meet this goal, the STADIEM consortium has devised an agile and lean impact assessment strategy based on the industry-standard start-up and innovation validation methodology of Build-Measure-Learn by Eric Ries¹, as well as on the Minimum Viable Pilot's approach representing "the fastest, simplest, and cheapest test of a desirable "innovation attribute" to determine — with the least possible effort — its most likely business value."

The STADIEM's Minimum Viable Impact Assessment (MVIA) strategy aims to be fast, simple, continuous, and experiment-based, to identify which critical impact factors and results are the most relevant in relation to the project's goals, and to devise rapidly deployable solutions or mitigation actions.

The MVIA methodology consists of four steps, displayed below in Figure 1:

- Step 1: Build – creation and deployment of the STADIEM project, programme and its components
- Step 2: Measure – identify, map, and measure the outcomes of activities deployed at the Build phase
- Step 3: Learn – learn from the outcomes, and identify and discuss mitigation actions at the task, work package, and/or consortium level

¹ Ries, Eric. 2011. *The Lean Start-up: How Today's Entrepreneurs Use Continuous Innovation to Create Radically Successful Businesses*. Crown.

- Step 4 Implement: implement mitigation actions, adjustments, or new components at the build phase
- Step 5: Repeat the process

FIGURE 1: STADIEM MINIMUM VIABLE IMPACT ASSESSMENT METHODOLOGY: CONTINUOUS BUILD, MEASURE, LEARN LOOP.

The MVIA strategy is derived from the project's initial impact assessment mapping in the grant proposal and is deployed continuously throughout the project's execution. Specifically, it focuses on three core areas of impact measuring, learning, and deployment:

- Core Area 1: Ecosystem impact. The impact is measured towards the European media sector and the open calls' objectives, and the STADIEM/mediatech ecosystem in Europe (hub, stakeholders, start-ups (/beneficiaries), and other ecosystem members – see D1.1 and D1.2 for an overview).
- Core Area 2: STADIEM framework and programme deployment impact. The impact is measured throughout open calls, framework deployment, programme deployment, including pilots, and the impact of/on stakeholders involved in those processes.
- Core Area 3: Dissemination impact. The impact is measured throughout the project's dissemination cycle, including visibility and media coverage, social media, events (self-organized and participated), and materials and publications.

FIGURE 2: STADIEM IMPACT MEASUREMENT AREAS

1.2 DESCRIPTION OF IMPACT ASSESSMENT AND A DETAILED BREAKDOWN

The responsibilities of impact assessment within the three focus areas described above, are divided between consortium members in their respective work area that also matches their separate work package. The breakdown is provided below:

- WP1 - Community of Ecosystems, VRT
- WP2 - STADIEM incubation and acceleration framework, Storytek, Exit Academy
- WP3 - Engaging Start-up/ SMEs, including Open Calls, F6S
- WP4 - STADIEM Programme, MCB, and stages (Match – NMA, Develop – VRT, Integrate – Storytek, Pilot – MCB)
- WP5 - Outreach and impact creation, Martel, with overall impact assessment – Storytek, Advisory board – NMA
- WP6 – Overall Project Management and Coordination, VRT

Impact data that illustrate the project's performance or require joint attention are collected by all consortium members and data points are managed centrally in a secured Google Drive environment.

The following table (Table 1) describes the critical impact collection points grouped in relation to the impact measurement areas, frequency, and collection method/repository.

Stage	Impact Action	Output	Frequency	Collection Form	KPI
Ecosystem Impact	Impact on broader ecosystem of cultural and creative industries, mediatech community and other stakeholders	STADIEM community & ecosystem Map	Twice per project	Community map in the project's repository in Google Drive, confidential deliverables D1.3 (M20) and D1.4 (M36), public deliverables D1.6 (M24) and D.1.7(M36) (public)	Twice per project (M20/M36)
	Impact on external stakeholders	Engagement calendar & log	Continuous	Engagement Calendar in Airtable	Ten networking meetings held between Hubs and stakeholders per hub per cohort
	Impact on the start-ups and scale-ups selected for the programme	Engagement calendar & log	Continuous	Engagement Calendar in Airtable	Ten networking meetings held between Hubs and stakeholders per hub per cohort
	Impact on investors/portfolio managers	Investor / Portfolio Manager Study	Once per cohort	Google Forms in the project's repository on Google Drive	At least 2 investor introductions per selected startup organized during the project
	Impact assessment from Advisory Board	Feedback to consortium	At least twice during the project	Notes from meetings with AB	75% AB members present

	Impact on local ecosystems	Local ecosystem reports	Once per cohort	Engagement calendar in Airtable	Ten networking meetings held between Hubs and stakeholders per hub per cohort
Framework & Programme deployment impact	Impact on hubs: Implementation of the STADIEM methodology	STADIEM framework & activity calendar	Continuous	Activity calendar & log in Airtable	
	Qualitative impact on the hubs	Workshop	Twice per project	Workshop outcomes, D2.3 and D2.4, and final report	
	Qualitative feedback from the start-ups and scale-ups selected for the programme	Stage report of start-ups and scale-ups selected for the programme (from Match phase onwards)	Once per phase	Stage questionnaire as part of stage performance evaluation	Min 75% of participant companies provide feedback
	Maturation of innovative technologies & business processes	TRL assessment post-cohort	Once per cohort	Cohort assessment report	
	Impact on improved crossborder business activities	Cross-border networking + pilot report	Once per cohort	Cohort assessment questionnaire in Airtable	
	Pilot quality	Corporate assessment survey	Once per cohort	Corporate assessment questionnaire in Airtable	Feedback response from at least one end user
	Impact on open calls	Open call report	Once per cohort	Open call deliverables D3.3 (M9)	

				and D3.4 (M20)	
Communication & Dissemination Impact	Media Dissemination Impact	Dissemination report	Once per reporting period	Dissemination report in project's repository in Google Drive, D5.8, D5.9	6 flyers + 4 posters 12 newsletters by end of project 4 videos (100 views) per year
	Website impact	Dissemination report	Once per reporting period	Dissemination report in project's repository in Google Drive	> 1,500 visitors (yearly average)
	Publication impact	Dissemination report	Once per reporting period	Dissemination report in project's repository in Google Drive	6 press releases by end of project
	Social media impact	Dissemination report	Once per reporting period	Dissemination report in project's repository in Google Drive	> 300 Twitter followers > 100 LinkedIn followers (yearly average)
	Presentation impact	Events report	Once per reporting period	Dissemination report in project's repository in Google Drive	At least 6 per year
	Event impact	Events Report	Once per reporting period	Dissemination report in project's repository on Google Drive	At least 6 per year 2 webinars per open call At least 4 Workshops to promote STADIEM

					and its findings to external stakeholders
					1 open final event (Demo Day)

TABLE 1 : STADIEM PROJECT IMPACT ASSESSMENT BREAKDOWN

1.3 PROCEDURES AND CONTRIBUTIONS FOR IMPACT DATA GATHERING AND MONITORING

The impact measurement, frequency, and collection method/repository are shared between the consortium partners. The overall responsibility for impact assessment methodology and report is designated to consortium partner Storytek who is also in charge of the project's framework development. The impact assessment duties are shared with WP leader Martel and collaborative tasks assigned at WP level during consortium meetings.

The following table (Table 2) describes the contributions of impact data gathering by the consortium partners.

Stage	Impact Action	Output	Collection Form	Main contributors
Ecosystem impact	Impact on mediatech community	STADIEM community & ecosystem map	Community map in the project's repository on Google Drive	All partners
	Impact on external stakeholders	Engagement calendar & log	Engagement Calendar in Airtable	All partners
	Impact on start-up community	Engagement calendar & log	Engagement Calendar in Airtable	All partners
	Impact on investors/portfolio managers	Investor / portfolio manager study	Google Forms in the project's repository on Google Drive	Storytek / Exit Academy
	Impact assessment from Advisory Board	Feedback to consortium	Advisory board notes in the project's repository on Google Drive	NMA
	Impact on Local ecosystems	Local ecosystem reports	Engagement calendar in Airtable	All partners

Framework & Programme Deployment Impact	Impact on hubs: Implementation of the STADIEM methodology	STADIEM framework & activity calendar	Activity calendar & log in Airtable	All partners
	Qualitative impact on the hubs	Workshop	Workshop outcomes, Deliverable 1.3, and final report	Storytek
	Qualitative feedback from the start-ups	Stage report of beneficiaries (from Match phase onwards)	Questionnaire per phase as part of the phase performance evaluation	Phase responsible partners, NMA, VRT, Storytek, MCB
	Maturation of innovative technologies & business processes	TRL assessment post-cohort	Cohort assessment report as part of project management deliverables	All hubs
	Impact on improved cross-border business activities	Cross border networking + pilot report	Cohort assessment questionnaire in Airtable	All hubs
	Pilot quality	Corporate assessment survey	Corporate assessment questionnaire in Airtable	All hubs
	Impact on open calls	Open call report	Open call deliverables	F6S
Communication & Dissemination Impact	Media dissemination impact	Dissemination report	Dissemination report in the project's repository on Google Drive	Martel Innovate
	Website impact	Dissemination report	Dissemination report in the project's repository on Google Drive	Martel Innovate
	Publication Impact	Dissemination report	Dissemination report in the project's repository on Google Drive	Martel Innovate

	Social Media Impact	Dissemination report	Dissemination report in project's repository on Google Drive	Martel Innovate
	Presentation Impact	Events Report	Dissemination report in project's repository on Google Drive	Martel Innovate
	Event Impact	Events Report	Dissemination report in project's repository on Google Drive	Martel Innovate

TABLE 2 : STADIEM PROJECT IMPACT ASSESSMENT RESPONSIBILITIES ALLOCATION

2 IMPACT METHODOLOGY IMPLEMENTATION

2.1 IMPACT MEASUREMENT PROCESS: FROM METHODOLOGY TO FINAL REPORT

The impact measurement and implementation during the STADIEM project are carried out using the Minimum Viable Impact Assessment methodology described in Section 1 of this deliverable. The following section describes in detail how the impact assessment procedure is executed through the life cycle of the project and translated into impact assessment deliverables:

- Community engagement, D1.5, D1.6, D1.7
- STADIEM framework and toolkit, D2.3, D2.4
- STADIEM open C-call reports, D3.3, D3.4
- Impact reports D5.4, D5.5
- Dissemination and outreach D5.8 and D5.9
- Management reports, D6.4, D.6.5, D6.6

FIGURE 3: STADIEM IMPACT MANAGEMENT PROCESS THROUGHOUT THE PROJECT

As can be seen from the Figure above, the impact measurement process is executed throughout the three-year project in the following steps.

Year 1:

- **Impact assessment brainstorming** - based on the initial impact methodology described in the grant application and revised during the meetings with the consortium, executed by impact lead Storytek
- **Impact assessment methodology** – is the outcome of the brainstorming sessions and the updating of the initial impact methodology, executed by impact lead Storytek
- **Confirmation of the impact assessment methodology** - the methodology is confirmed by all consortium members and delivered as D5.3
- **Set up questionnaire and data gathering templates** – this activity is carried out synchronously with the impact assessment brainstorming and methodology creation to develop detailed questionnaires and data gathering templates. This process is executed by impact lead Storytek and validated by consortium members.
- **Encode templates to software tools** – the validated questionnaires and templates are encoded to relevant platforms and tools by consortium member MCB responsible for tools management in the project.
- **Gather impact data** – the impact leader and contributors gather data through data points described in this deliverable.

Year 2:

- **Gather impact data** (continues) – the impact leader and contributors gather data through data points described in this deliverable.
- **Analyze impact** – first, and assigned consortium members analyze second-year impact data, and critical lessons are implemented on a running basis to the project.
- **Produce interim impact reports & deliverables** – relevant reports and deliverables are produced.

Year 3:

- **Gather impact data** (continues) – the impact leader and contributors gather data through data points described in this deliverable.
- **Analyze impact** –third-year impact data is analyzed by assigned consortium members, and critical lessons are implemented on a running basis to the project.
- **Produce final impact reports & deliverables** – final reports and deliverables are produced along with the project's closing impact assessment.

3 CONCLUSION

The primary goal of this deliverable was to present the impact assessment methodology for STADIEM as an ambitious business scaling project for mediatech start-ups selected for the programme.

The methodology presented was derived from the original grant proposal, revised through research by impact lead Storytek, debated and discussed by the consortium partners at a Consortium Meeting, and implemented in total capacity during the project's second year.

It should be noted that while the overall methodology concept is filed as of this deliverable, much of the impact assessment in practical terms has been ongoing since the beginning of the project in various data points (such as community map, start-up performance, and feedback – gathered on ad hoc basis and at the end of each phase, Advisory Board feedback - gathered during Advisory Board meetings, and overall consortium performance feedback – gathered throughout the project, open calls feedback – filed as deliverable, dissemination feedback – picked continuously, etc.). This deliverable synthesized the ongoing impact assessment processes and proposed a holistic framework for the impact assessment to be streamlined and consolidated.

This deliverable thus paves the way for the publication of STADIEM's exciting findings from the European scale-up landscape in the form of the STADIEM updated framework toolkit, open call, and further reports.

4 REFERENCES

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